

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidative regeneration of carbonyl compounds from oximes by quinolinium bromochromate

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Abstract : The oxidative deoxygenation of several aldo- and keto-oximes by quinolinium bromochromate (QBC), in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO), exhibited a first order dependence on both the oxime and QBC. The oxidation of ketoximes is slower than that of aldoximes. The rates of oxidation of aldoximes correlated well in terms of Pavelich-Taft dual substituent-parameter equation. The low positive value of polar reaction constant indicated a nucleophilic attack by a chromate-oxygen on the carbon. The reaction is subject to steric hindrance by the alkyl groups. The reaction of acetaldoxime has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect has been analysed by multiparametric equations. A mechanism involving the formation of a cyclic intermediate, in the rate-determining step, has been proposed.

Keywords : Structure rate correlation, correlation analysis, oxidative regeneration.

Regeneration of carbonyl compounds from its derivatives under mild conditions is an important process in synthetic organic chemistry. Several oxidative methods are available for deoxygenation¹. Quinolinium bromochromate (QBC), has been used as an mild and selective oxidant in synthetic organic chemistry². Only a few reports about the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of oxidation by QBC are available in the literature³. In continuation of earlier work⁴, we report here the kinetics of the oxidative deoxygenation of several aldo- and keto-oximes by QBC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO). Mechanistic aspects are discussed.

Experimental

Materials : Oximes were prepared by the reported standard methods⁵ and their m.p. were checked with the literature values. QBC also was prepared by the reported method². Solvents were purified by the usual procedure⁶.

Product analysis : The oxidation of the oximes results in the regeneration of corresponding carbonyl compounds, as confirmed by TLC (eluent : CCl₄/Et₂O). Isolation of the product was attempted in the oxidation of oximes of benzaldehyde and acetophenone. In a typical experiment, the oxime (0.2 mol) and QBC (0.02 mol) were dissolved in 50 ml of DMSO and allowed to stand for *ca.* 10 h for the completion of the reaction. Silica gel (5 g) was then added to the reaction mixture and the mixture was stirred

for 15 min⁷. It was then filtered and the solid residue was washed with the solvent (2 × 15 ml). The solvent was removed on a rotary evaporator and the residue was purified on a silica-gel column (eluent : CCl₄/Et₂O). Evaporation of the solvent afforded the pure carbonyl compound. Yields of benzaldehyde and acetophenone were 1.77 g (83%) and 2.11 g (88%) respectively. The products were converted into their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones (DNP). The identity of DNP was confirmed by determining their m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic samples. Oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixture, determined by an iodometric method, is 3.96 ± 0.06.

Kinetics measurements : The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess of the oxime over QBC. The solvent was DMSO, unless mentioned otherwise. The reactions were studied at constant temperature (±0.1 K), and followed for up to 80% completion by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of QBC spectrophotometrically at 365 nm. The pseudo-first order rate constant, *k*_{obs}, was evaluated from the linear least-squares plots of log [QBC] versus time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed the rate constants to be reproducible to within ±3%. We have used coefficient of determination (*R*² or *r*²), standard deviation (*sd*) and Exner's parameter, *ψ*, as the measures of goodness of fit⁸.

Results and discussion

The rate and other experimental data were obtained for all the oximes studied. Since the results are similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

Stoichiometry : The analysis of products indicated the following overall reaction.

QBC undergoes a two-electron change, which is in accord earlier observation with pyridinium and quinolinium halochromates⁴.

Rate laws : The reaction is first order with respect to QBC. The individual kinetic runs yielded linear ($r^2 > 0.995$) plots between $\log [\text{QBC}]$ and time. Further, the values of k_{obs} do not depend on the initial concentration of QBC. The reaction exhibited a linear dependence on the concentration of the oximes (Table 1). A constancy in the values of k_2 at $61.3 \pm 0.8 \times 10^{-4}$ (where $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{oxime}]$) confirmed that the reaction is first order with respect to the oxime as well.

Effect of temperature : The rate constants were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2).

Effect of solvents : The oxidation of acetaldoxime was studied in nineteen different solvents. The choice of solvents was limited by the solubility of the reactants and the reaction of QBC with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with chosen solvents. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 3.

The linear correlation ($r^2 = 0.9962$) between the values of the activation enthalpies and entropies of the reaction

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of acetaldoxime by QBC at 308 K

$10^3 [\text{QBC}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Oxime] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	0.1	12.4
1.0	0.2	23.8
1.0	0.4	47.0
1.0	0.6	71.1
1.0	0.8	95.4
1.0	1.0	119
0.5	0.4	48.0
2.0	0.4	46.7
3.0	0.4	48.6
4.0	0.4	47.2
5.0	0.4	46.8

indicated the operation of a significant compensation effect in this reaction⁹. The reaction exhibited an excellent isokinetic effect (temperature 425 ± 10) also, as determined by Exner's method¹⁰. An Exner's plot between $\log k_2$ at 288 K and at 318 K is linear ($r^2 = 0.9992$, slope = 0.7366 ± 0.01). The value of isokinetic temperature is 449 ± 10 K. A linear isokinetic relationship is a necessary condition for the validity of linear free energy relationships. It also implies that all reactions so correlated follow a similar mechanism¹⁰.

The rate constants, k_2 , of the oxidation of acetaldoxime in eighteen solvents (CS_2 was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (2) of Kamlet *et al.*¹¹,

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (2)$$

Table 2. Rate constant and activation parameters for the oxidation of oximes ($\text{R}^1\text{R}^2\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{OH}$) by QBC

Substituent	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
	288	298	308	318 K				
H	H	981	1130	1260	1440	17.0 ± 0.2	-240 ± 1	78.4 ± 0.2
H	Me	58.8	85.0	119	171	24.4 ± 0.4	-203 ± 1	84.8 ± 0.3
H	Et	46.8	69.3	99.9	153	27.3 ± 0.8	-195 ± 2	85.3 ± 0.6
H	Pr	26.3	41.4	62.1	97.2	30.4 ± 0.5	-189 ± 2	86.6 ± 0.4
H	Pr ¹	19.1	32.0	49.5	79.2	33.2 ± 0.4	-182 ± 1	87.3 ± 0.3
H	ClCH ₂	108	144	182	234	16.9 ± 0.4	-224 ± 1	83.5 ± 0.3
H	Ph	162	245	378	585	30.1 ± 0.6	-175 ± 2	82.2 ± 0.5
Me	Me	3.51	6.48	11.7	21.6	43.5 ± 0.6	-161 ± 2	91.2 ± 0.5
Me	Et	2.77	5.22	9.63	18.0	44.8 ± 0.6	-158 ± 2	91.7 ± 0.4
Et	Et	2.18	4.25	8.01	15.3	46.8 ± 0.5	-153 ± 2	92.2 ± 0.4
Me	Ph	14.4	19.1	27.0	36.9	21.6 ± 0.7	-225 ± 2	88.4 ± 0.5

Table 3. Effect of solvent on the oxidation of acetaldoxime by QBC at 308 K

Solvent	$10^4 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)	Solvent	$10^4 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)
Chloroform	43.6	Toluene	6.46
1,2-Dichloroethane	39.8	Acetophenone	38.0
Dichloromethane	35.5	Tetrahydrofuran	12.6
DMSO	119	<i>t</i> -BuOH	18.2
Acetone	33.1	Dioxane	14.8
Dimethylformamide	52.5	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	7.95
Butanone	22.4	Acetic acid	22.4
Nitrobenzene	41.7	Ethyl acetate	12.6
Benzene	9.54	Carbon disulfide	11.2
Cyclohexane	0.66		

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of (2), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below [(3)–(6)].

$$\log k_2 = -3.93 + 1.92 (\pm 0.20)\pi^* + 0.12 (\pm 0.17)\beta + 0.44 (\pm 0.16)\alpha \quad (3)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8837; sd = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.22$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.04 + 1.76 (\pm 0.23)\pi^* + 0.27 (\pm 0.19)\beta \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8194; sd = 0.22; n = 18; \psi = 0.45$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.09 + 1.83 (\pm 0.23)\pi^* \quad (5)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7942; sd = 0.23; n = 18; \psi = 0.47$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.94 + 0.59 (\pm 0.39)\beta \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1221; sd = 0.47; n = 18; \psi = 0.96$$

Kamlet's triparametric equation explains *ca.* 88% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion the correlation is not even satisfactory (*cf.* 3). The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 79% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation¹² of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also (7).

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (7)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of

(7), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 1.54 (\pm 0.03)A + 1.72 (\pm 0.02)B - 4.30 \quad (8)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9976; sd = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.05$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.30 (\pm 0.57)A - 3.12 \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.2349; sd = 0.46; n = 19; \psi = 0.90$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.60 (\pm 0.27)B - 3.80 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.6693; sd = 0.30; n = 19; \psi = 0.59$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.66 \pm 0.03(A+B) - 3.71 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9944; sd = 0.04; n = 19; \psi = 0.07$$

The rates of oxidation of acetaldoxime in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation with both the anion- and cation-solvating powers playing almost equal role. However, individually A and B are able to account for only 23 and 66% of the data only. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also exhibited an excellent correlation. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 99% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not very significant ($r^2 = 0.4553$; $sd = 0.39$; $\psi = 0.76$).

Correlation analysis of reactivity :

We could not find any report about the mechanism of the reaction between a C=N bond and a halochromate derivative. However, the reaction of alkenes with chromium(VI) has been well studied¹³. Since, olefinic bonds are not usually subject to a nucleophilic attack, it has been suggested that in the alkene-chromate reaction, an organometallic derivative is formed initially¹³. The organometallic derivative then changes to a chromium(IV) diester in the rate-determining step. However, carbon-nitrogen double bonds, being dipolar in nature, can be easily attacked by a nucleophile. The data in Table 2 showed that the rate of oxidation of ketoximes is much less as compared to that of the aldoximes. The reason for the slower reaction of ketoximes must be steric. As the central carbon changes from a trigonal to a tetragonal state, the crowding around it increases. This increase in the steric crowding will be more in the case of ketoximes as compared to that in aldoximes. This observation is supported by the correlation analysis of the reactivity of the aliphatic aldoximes also. The rate of oxidation of the aliphatic aldoximes did not yield significant correlation separately with Taft's σ^* and E_s values [(12) and (13)].

$$\log k_2 = 1.05 \pm 0.28 \sigma^* - 2.68 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.6692, sd = 0.44, n = 6, \psi = 0.61,$$

$$\text{temp.} = 308 \text{ K}$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.84 \pm 0.06 E_s - 2.92 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9679, sd = 0.14, n = 6, \psi = 0.19,$$

$$\text{temp.} = 308 \text{ K}$$

The rates were, therefore, correlated with Pavelich-Taft's¹⁴ dual substituent-parameter eq. (14).

$$\log k_2 = \rho^* \sigma^* + \delta E_s + \log k_0 \quad (14)$$

The rates exhibited excellent correlations in terms of the Pavelich-Taft equation (Table 4); the reaction constants are being positive.

The low positive polar reaction constant points to an almost cyclic transition state in which the formation of the bond between chromate-oxygen and the carbon is somewhat ahead of the formation of N-O bond. This supports a nucleophilic attack by a chromate-oxygen on the carbon. The positive steric reaction constant points to a steric hindrance by the substituents. Therefore, the following mechanism (Scheme 1) is proposed for the reaction. The mechanism is supported by the values of activation parameters also. The low values of enthalpy of activation indicate that the bond-cleavage and bond-formation are almost synchronous. The large negative entropies of activation support the formation of a rigid cyclic activated complex from two acyclic molecules.

The faster oxidation of benzaldoxime may be attributed to the resonance stabilization of the cyclic activated complex. The oxidation of benzophenoxime is much slower. This may well be due to steric hindrance by the bulky phenyl and methyl groups.

Scheme 1

Hydroxynitrene (N-OH) has been recently reported as a very reactive intermediate¹⁵.

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Table 4. Reaction constants for the oxidative deoxygenation of aliphatic aldoximes by QBC^a

Temp./K	ρ^*	δ	R^2	sd	ψ
288	0.44 ± 0.01	0.81 ± 0.01	0.9999	0.008	0.01
298	0.39 ± 0.01	0.75 ± 0.01	0.9998	0.001	0.02
308	0.32 ± 0.02	0.69 ± 0.02	0.9989	0.003	0.04
318	0.26 ± 0.02	0.63 ± 0.01	0.9998	0.007	0.02

^aNumber of compound is 6.

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